

STRATEGIES FOR TEACHING MULTILINGUAL TEAMWORK IN DIFFERENT PROFESSIONS

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This thesis presents the scientific and theoretical basis of the strategies of this direction in the current training and seminars aimed at developing multilingual professions and forming collective cooperation. Currently, in the conditions of globalization and the development of the labor market as a result of the integration of artificial intelligence and smart technologies in communicative approaches, intercultural cooperation and training projects for effective cooperation in multilingual teams, as well as developing professional, social and collective skills of learners using advanced technologies in this field. The result of the research serve as the methodological basis of this direction

In the revolutionized and rapidly changing world owing a specific profession is hard to reach because of new and smart technologies. For that case, in the labor market while many fields have their own challenges, in today's developing world, there are many demands to require commitment to the professions people hold and the determination and creation of multilingual work environments in the age of human-replacing technologies. These hardwork can create cozy atmosphere not only for job owners but it can also develop their culture, behavior by cooperating with other countries.

To introduce with the main idea, learning or being multilingual can gain benefit to us, by protecting from many diseases like Alzheimer and Dementia. The main purpose is avoiding from memory loss, by reading or learning many languages can increase the brain fibers and helps the transferring information to long-term memory and it protects against existing diseases. We can see many benefits of this topic in many ways, but this was a biological description of language learning.

There are many professions in the world but many of them are nowadays demanding updates and changes in the field of being multilingual in order to have worldwide cooperating system. To begin with, building multilingual teamwork in the education system demands professionals with pedagogical approaches that helps to avoid old traditional teaching methods. And this researched learning methods helps actively on creating enthusiasm on more children in the way of approaching teachercentred or lecture-oriented methods [3,p. 4], instead of appearing boring stuff, learning and teaching are nowadays easy because of new learning methods like online lessons, trainings and even it puts your needs first by creating competitive atmosphere and working with teamwork. By using these revolutionized methods in which students work together in groups, they become more active participants in their own learning rather than owing a passive knowledge [3, p.4] From 2020 year in Uzbekistan many educational systems had cooperations with different countries like USA. The main purpose was teaching students in different languages and working with teamwork . As a result, they organized many extra courses and even made theatres or movie clubs in order to help students express their opinions freely and discussing by listening each other carefully.

Returning 1966, when all of this phenomenon became one of the most successful and widespread application of small-group training of teachers at the University of Minnesota by experiencing them in different modes, especially, Games Tournament, Student Teams Achievement Division and many group investigations involved to enhance that strategies [1, p.365]. Therefore, the theory of unskilled group members are denied as it said that they can not cooperate effectively because worldwide cooperations needs skilled teamworks as well, for that reason, students must be taught and motivated the interpersonal and small group skills to provide or hold high-quality cooperations. To achieve mutual goals, students and co-workers should trust and get to know each other well, accept and support and resolve conflicts constructively [1, p.369].

In the field of modern digital socio-economic interactions, as human relations can not be built without communication and cooperation we are all trying to learn many different cultures and languages in order to travel also. This interactions between all cultures creates the basis of integrated worldview, values and social issues (religion, economics and politics) and each field indirectly affect to social distance between the representatives of different cultures [2, p.9]. And this cultural differences are represented by values, behavior and representatives to play a very special role in teambuilding, cooperations, decision making and organization of working processes and to go against with that idea to improve that differences and as combination of this problems comes cooperations of being multilingual approachments [2, p.9].

In the field of business section, it is urgent to learn and be multilingual because all of job owners who are involved to this section can wish worldwide interactions. Business women and men who are having this skill are nearly tend to create or start their financial plan, a communication strategies in order to handle many crisis and press contacts and this can offer from external partners to gain support or co-working atmosphere. To have a chance as being a part of team in this field, the chairman or company owners need to create or have this prior education background. For that reason, prospective students who do have prior knowledge of economics take a modified and less extensive module [4]. Additionally to that, Germany is known for its best teaching system and it creates to business and economy professions special offer to learn French, English and even Spanish and these courses units are all about teaching all professions to convert with special duties into purposeful and efficient communication style in the field of making corporative interactions worldwide.

Multilingualism in the field of medicine creates an atmosphere where healthcare professionals and worldwide cooperative contacts can freely keep in touch with each other in order to solve or create many medicine or cure to diseases. Many scientific evidences indicates that language barriers can also have a negative impact on the rate of error diagnostics, longer hospital stays and lower patient satisfaction. As one country which does not cure that one disease, we can handle it from another, for that reason, in order not to have an error treatment ,firstly, all patients and doctors should have at least one language preference not to make any treatment in a wrong way and it will be a provider communication by obtaining more accurate medical histories and facilitating shared decision-making. And having that one increases patient trust, improves their health literacy and this is the evidence collectively contribute to health improvement and reduced healthcare disparities.

Multilingualism also plays a crucial role in international collaborations, disease surveillance, health education as Uzbekistan reveals the best medical teaching system students

likely from India are willing and they learning this basic keys in order to gave humanitarian response. And it creates a friendly atmosphere with international collaborative stuff in the field of researches to diseases that can many people survive. For that reason, being multilingual or learning other languages emphasize the best solutions to have friendly interactions with other countries.

References:

1. Teaching and Assessing Intercultural Communicative Competence Revisited 2nd edition Michael Byram : p. 365-369;
2. Multilingual Education: Development of Professional Foreign Language Communicative Competence of Students in a Digital Environment: p. 9;
3. Cooperative Learning : Theory and Practice : p.4;
4. <https://share.google/ulKylJH2lWYt8shEb>